

Review

Consumer Behaviour, Historical Development of the Consumer Movement and a Theoretical Approach to Universal Consumer Rights

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Abstract

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The aim of this study is to explain the universal consumer rights by talking about the historical development of the consumer movement. It is possible to say that consumer movements started with the start of trade. However, with today's understanding, it is said that consumer rights were first initiated by the American President Kenedy in the 1960s. However, according to the researches, it is possible to say that consumer rights were given importance in other countries in the past.

Keywords: Consumer Behaviour, Consumer's Purchasing Process, Consumer Rights, Factors Affecting Consumer Behavior

INTRODUCTION

Consumer behavior covers many bases. Consumer behavior is a concept that consists of processes involving the selection, purchase, use and possession of products, ideas, services and experiences in order to meet the needs and desires of people or groups (Solomon, 1995, s. 7).

Today, consumers want to know more about the goods and services they receive, pay attention to quality and know their rights very well. Unpredictable expectations are flexible and carry an endless desire for absolute good quality (Jolson, 1988, s. 15).

In general, the consumers you are looking at now know very well what they want. Consumers now want to shop from sellers who can think multi-purpose, want to know not only the product, but also the brand and institution, and are not an error-free product, marketer or brand; accept their mistake, empathize, read consumer behavior. For this reason, it is of great importance to address the development of consumer behavior today and to evaluate consumer behavior within the framework of universal consumer rights in order to reveal the current situation. In this study, consumer behavior and effective

factors were discussed and universal consumer rights were evaluated.

Literature Research

Description of the Consumer

From the point of view of marketing, the work with the consumer is usually dealt with in the aspect of material needs. But, as well as material needs, emotional and mental needs should also be given importance. The concept of consumption is generally perceived as consumption in a material sense. But besides material consumption, there are intangible consumption items such as entertainment and culture (Altunışık, Özdemir and Torlak, Modern Pazarlama, 2006, s. 59).

"As a consumer unit that creates the Sunday in marketing, the customer is an individual, institution and organization with a need to be satisfied, money to spend and a desire to spend" (Mucuk, 1997, s. 74). In other words, "The consumer is someone who uses or

consumes products and services not for the purpose of producing other goods and services, but purely for their individual or family needs" (Tek and Özgül, 2005, s. 163). According to another definition " " Consumers are real people who purchase or have the capacity to purchase marketing components in order to meet their individual desires, desires and requirements" (Karabulut, 1981, s. 11). In other words, "a consumer is a person who is equipped with a requirement, has tastes and can make a choice, uses economic resources to buy products and services, and achieves satisfaction by providing benefits as a result of these actions" (Zengin, 2012, s. 33).

In other words, consumers are real people who have certain needs, have a desire to meet these needs, buy or are inclined to buy products or services aimed at meeting their needs. The concept of consumer is a comprehensive word. Individuals, families, producer organizations, seller organizations, legal entities, non-profit institutions, public institutions, etc. it is considered as a consumer. Consumers are divided into two groups according to their intention to purchase goods on the sunday: end consumers and industrial/organizational consumers. Those who perform the act of purchasing in order to satisfy individual or family needs enter the final consumer class. On the other hand, those who perform the purchase action for production, commercial and economic reasons are called industrial consumers (Mucuk, 1997, s. 74). The main difference between these groups; people who purchase individual or family needs due to final consumers for their own use, while commercial and industrial consumers in order to continue producing that performs the action the person or purchase of operating organizations. There are different roles in a sunday, including "consumer", "decision maker", "buyer" and "influencing them". For example, a student who continues his education in a private school, from this point of view, is a "consumer", a family that covers the costs of education is a "decision maker", and those who advise a student to go to that school are in an "impressive" role (Taşkın, 2000, s. 19). The given example has dealt with different roles of the consumer concept. In this example, the consumer is a student here because the person receiving the service, that is, using the educational service, is a student. Since the costs of this educational service are covered by the family, not the student, the family is in the decision-making role. The people who recommend this school to the family play an impressive role, as it affects the family in some way.

Factors Affecting Consumer Behavior

Personal Elements

Profession, economic situation, age, personality and lifestyle make up personal factors. One of the most important demographic qualities, age, has a great

influence on consumers' purchasing decisions. In october, the age element divides consumers into certain subcultures. For example, for older people, such as healthy lifestyle and health products. Marketers pay attention to this when choosing their target sunday and prepare appropriate goods and marketing strategies for it (Tek, 1999, s. 204). Especially in countries with a high young population, such as Turkey, consumption is promising

The profession is also an indicator of the level of education of an individual. Profession is a factor that significantly affects the decision of individuals to purchase. The economic situation increases its importance, especially in expensive goods, such as the purchase of vehicles. It is quite difficult to buy a car for a person whose economic situation can only afford to meet his basic requirements. However, it should be remembered that the current economic power is insufficient to buy a car, and consumers who will move to the high-income group in the future are in the position of potential buyers (Tek, 1999, s. 205).

The way of life of an individual, his actions, interests are the model of the world in which he lives in his head. The lifestyle reflects the social class of the person on the one hand, and the character on the other (Kotler, 2000, s. 168). Even people who have the same social class, subculture and even the same profession can have very different lifestyles. The lifestyle of an individual is a lifestyle that finds expression in his activities, interests and thoughts (Tek, 1999, s. 204). Determining the lifestyle has many advantages. People with similar lifestyles exhibit similar consumption behaviors.

Karabulut defined personality as a unique system that allows to distinguish one individual from another and embodies all his internal and external qualities (Karabulut, 1981, s. 124). another definition is as follows: the whole set of special and typical behaviors that distinguish an individual from others is called a personality. Everyone has a personality, and this personality also affects their buying behavior. Personality can be extremely useful when analyzing consumer behavior in some product and brand preferences.

Psychological Elements

The power that arises from the individual himself and affects his behavior is called the psychological factor. The main psychological factors are as follows (İlban, Akkılıç, & Özer, 2011, s. 39):

- Motivation
- Perception
- Learning
- Personality.

*Motivation (Motive):*The word motivation/motive, defined as the state of the stimulus, with stimulating energy to achieve a goal, is derived from the Latin word "movere

(Güney, 2015, s. 8). Motivated consumers are considered energetic, ready and eager to engage in goal-related activity (Öztürk and Çakır, 2015, s. 317). At the core of all the behavior of individuals lies motives. Motive refers to the state of the organism that initiates, directs and maintains its action, and directs the organism towards a certain goal. The motive is formed as a result of the initiation of a requirement. After the motive is formed and saturated, it does not disappear completely and reappears after a while. This condition is called the cyclical nature of the motive. Motivation determines the orientation to this behavior. The need that is felt first turns into a motive by impulse, and the motive also triggers the orientation to behavior (Öztürk and Çakır, 2015). The motive, which is a force that mobilizes the consumer in the purchase of goods, puts it into action by setting out the goal, is actually the cause of the behavior. A negative state that is found in an individual whose need for consumption has not been completely eliminated triggers purposeful behavior. For this reason, consumer behavior and motivation are two closely related elements. The motive in the position of the driving force (driving factors) behind the behavior of individuals increases the desire of individuals to buy due to the influence of work and external stimuli (attractive factors). The elements of motive have taken on a repulsive and attractive role over persons. These factors explain how individuals are pushed by some elements when making a purchase decision on the one hand, and how they are attracted by some brands on the other (Demir & Kozak, 2011, s. 19). Highly motivated individuals are willing to achieve their goals, to do what they want. For example, someone with a high motivation to buy a good car asks for advice from their surroundings, conducts research, or goes to a car dealership and takes a test drive. It seems that he spends time and energy on these actions. Motivation not only leads to performing behaviors related to the goal, but also creates a desire to spend time and energy related to this behavior. When consumers are highly motivated in achieving their goals, they pay much more attention to it, turn to receiving all the information presented about it and try to remember this information in order to use it later.

Perception: The study of how sensory information is integrated with the perception of objects and how it is used when experiencing these perceptions is called "perception". Perception occurs when a stimulus is encountered for the first time, and sensations take shape as a result of this encounter. This shaping is influenced by many factors, especially attention, and these effects are of interest to cognitive studies.

Learning: The ability of individuals to continue their lives and fulfill the requirements of life, in other words, to become self-sufficient, is a qualification achieved over time. Almost all of these competencies are achieved through learning (Engin, Calapoğlu, & Gürbüzöğlü, 2015, s. 255). An individual's adventure in the world begins without bringing any information with it in advance, and

the person enters into a learning and adaptation process starting from the moment he is born (Oruç, 2010, s. 133). Almost all of the behavior of individuals is acquired through learning. As long as a person exists, the learning process also continues to exist. A very small part of behavior is born in the form of a reflex (Demir and Kozak, 2011, s. 43). Learning is a process that leads people to make non-stop efforts to produce new behaviors, acquire new information, and share this information (Akgün, 2010, s. 67). According to another approach, learning is expressed as a process related to the life that causes a change in behavior, attitude, knowledge in a person. There are important points that are highlighted in the definitions related to learning. These points are (Demir & Kozak, 2011, s. 44):

- Learning is a change in behavior.
- In order for learning to happen, this change must be quite permanent.
- In order for learning to occur, there must be some kind of repetition or experience.
- This repetition or experience needs to be reinforced in any way.

The main task of the consumer is to learn consumer activities that will bring the maximum possible benefit to himself. Learning how to use a new brand, performing the most reasonable and logical purchase action is related to learning theory. When a consumer gains a positive experience from any shopping, he learns about the behavior related to consumption. For this reason, institutions compete with each other to provide positive experiences to their customers (Zengin, 2012, s. 43).

Attitudes and Beliefs: Attitude occurs through learning and affects both behavior and social perception. Individuals form their own beliefs and attitudes after action and learning (Yükselen, 2013, s. 133). Some attitude qualities can be listed as follows:

- ♣ Attitudes are not innate, they are acquired later
- ♣ Each attitude has an object
- ♣ One attitude may be connected with another attitude
- ♣ Attitudes are formed through the way of learning
- ♣ Attitudes can change and be changed
- ♣ There may be decoherence between one attitude and other attitudes.

It is impossible to see the attitude with the eye, it can only be understood through the behavior of the individual, it is shaped by beliefs, values and thoughts. This relationship is shown below.

Social Elements

Reference groups include friends, trainers, important or famous people, especially family members, who have a direct or indirect effect on the behavior of consumers, according to the individual. Sometimes this scope is expanded and group phenomena such as social class,

culture, subculture and wild culture are also included. Consumers are influenced by many groups when making a purchase decision. The reason why a person is affected by more than one group is that a person's needs cannot be met by a single group, and each group specializes in its own goal. A person uses these groups when expressing his own value judgments, beliefs and thoughts. That is why solidarity groups can be defined as a community of individuals who form a point of view that is thought to shape a person's attitudes and obvious behaviors (Berkman and Gilson, 1992, s. 153).

Undoubtedly, the place of the family in the group of social influences is quite important. Many issues affecting consumer behavior are instilled in individuals by their parents. A person forgets some of these issues that his family has been exposed to over time, and leaves some of them because he doesn't like it. But he protects some of these issues and keeps them in the family that he will create himself. A union formed by blood, adoption or marriage as a result of two or more people living in the same house is called a family (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2004, s. 234). There are two types of family forms-core and broad. Families are consumer decision-making organizations with significant effects. A person experiences the purchase process within the framework of the political, economic and religious understandings that he has received from his family (Kılıç & Aykut, 2004, s. 62).

The position of individuals in groups such as the family and association they have joined can be taken into account in terms of status and role. For example, a woman is in the role of a product manager at the workplace where she works, while for her parents she is in the role of a daughter. All of these roles affect purchasing behavior. Each role represents a status in society. Products can also serve as a status symbol depending on the geographical situation, social class and even time. In the Turkey of the 50s and 60s, wearing jeans or smoking American cigarettes was a status symbol (Tek, 1999, s. 203).

The Consumer's Purchasing Process

Realizing The Need: The requirement activates the consumer when there is enough pressure to eliminate the need, regardless of the source. Consumers are exploring methods of eliminating their requirements. In order to purchase a product or service, you must first find or be alerted to the need. Since physiological requirements arise spontaneously, there is little need for their stimulation. But since there are many alternatives to eliminating the need for hunger, which is a physiological need, it is necessary to make an effort to direct the individual to a particular product or service. An individual can satisfy his thirst with buttermilk, water or another drink. For a business that wants to increase water sales,

this physiological requirement alone is not enough (Karafakioğlu, 2006, s. 105). "Internal (physiological, psychological, etc.) or external (sight, hearing, touch, etc.) it starts with stimuli. Institutions should investigate how needs are directed to goods" (Tek and Özgül, Modern Pazarlama İlkeleri, 2005, s. 185).

Information Collection: Consumers who have a problem feel or do not feel the need to collect more information about how they can solve this problem in the most reasonable way. If the pain caused by the problem is very severe and the object that will satisfy it is nearby, it can go down the path of buying that object without the need to find out more. But if the pressure is not too much, and the object in question is not coming soon, the consumer stores his requirement in his memory. In other words, it either does not get more information or it does research to get more information (Oluç, 2006, s. 761-762).

The process begins with the individual's need. But if the individual's impulse is strong, he can meet his requirement with the product he first found without research. If he does not buy it as soon as he first sees it, he stores the requirement in his memory. The severity of the consumer's impulse, whether he likes to do research, the ease of accessing the information he desires, the necessity and importance of obtaining information determine the level of research he will do. As we move from limited problem solving (low interest) to intensive problem solving (high interest), the need for research increases. Commercial stimulants, which are sources of information retrieval by an individual, are called "marketer-dominated sources of information". The most effective sources of information are word of mouth (word of mouth) and information obtained on advice (Tek, 1999, s. 213).

Evaluating Options: After consumers have learned about all the alternatives, they evaluate this information in the light of different criteria and choose the most suitable product. Consumers take into account certain qualities when choosing between alternatives and place them in an order of importance according to dec (Karafakioğlu, 2006, s. 106). It is very important for marketers to decipher how consumers choose from alternatives. Because a marketer who knows what criteria the evaluation is based on can influence the consumer's choice. When evaluating alternatives, it is very important to decipher what are the characteristics and qualities of the evaluation criteria, how the criteria are evaluated and how to choose from the alternatives (İslamoğlu and Altunışık, 2008, s. 43).

A Buying Decision: Consumers evaluate the alternatives at the end of the specified stages and temporarily make the decision to purchase the product that they find most suitable for themselves. For different reasons, such as the inability of the selected brand to be at the point of sale, the final decision may differ from this. In this case, the consumer can turn to the second best

alternative that has been determined by where to look for that brand. The actual purchase may be delayed until the place of purchase is selected or the price is negotiated. He may also encounter unexpected events such as being out of the consumer business and decreasing income. Meeting another requirement may be of greater importance. In addition, a co-friend can indicate whether he has used this brand before or not; family members can find the price of the product high and tell him to switch to a more suitable brand (Oluç, 2006, s. 766). Even if consumers have made a purchase decision, such factors can affect the purchase process. The purchase can take place either planned or unplanned. If the product to be purchased is intended for a general requirement, the product and brand have been determined, this is a planned purchase. On the other hand, this is an unplanned buying behavior if the purchase takes place during the purchase, without specifying a requirement and with no intention of buying (Argan, 2012, s. 171).

Post-Purchase Behavior: The main reason why individuals buy goods is to meet their requirements. If the consumer's requirement is not satisfied after using the product, a negative evaluation will result. Consumers may encounter three important situations after using a product they have purchased. These (Odabaşı & Barış, 2007, s. 387):

- He was satisfied (there is a high probability of buying the same brand or product again).
- He is partially satisfied (He is in cognitive contradiction).
- He is not satisfied (He is in complaining behavior).

Whether consumers are satisfied with the product or brand they are buying or not, it looks at whether the product or brand they are buying provides the benefit they are hoping for. In other words, a person is satisfied if the real benefit is the same as the benefit he hopes for, he is happy if the real benefit is above the benefit he hopes for, he is not satisfied if the real benefit is below the benefit he hopes for. In other words, the level of dissatisfaction of consumers with the product or brand is directly proportional to the level of the negative difference between the expected benefit and the actual benefit. What marketers should pay attention to here is not to increase consumers' expectations with unreal information. Such a situation leads to the fact that the expectations of the consumer are not met, which leads to the fact that the consumer will never choose this product or brand again (Karafakioğlu, 2006, s. 108).

Development and Consumer Choice in the Consumer Movement

Consumers have certain vital needs as individuals. For example, food products will always be in demand products. But here, too, product quality and brand choice force enterprises to compete. In addition, the constantly

changing needs, desires, desires and demands of individuals force businesses to constantly change. The rational consumer assumption, which is one of the ideas of classical economics, has lost its relevance. Accordingly, when buying a product or service, the consumer realizes his purchasing behavior by examining all its characteristics and comparing it with other products and services. Although this is true for conscious consumers, some product types, such as electronic products, emotional factors have been ignored with the endless information source provided by information technologies. The consumer makes his final decision, influenced by a very complex group of factors. This decision usually applies to that time and place. The instantaneous nature of purchasing behavior confronts enterprises with constant competition and actions to predict the future. In some cases, the consumer is not even able to fully predict his need for the product. That is why enterprises should make their reviews multidimensional when developing a product or designing a service. Modern societies are now full of individuals who can easily switch between brands, have flexible characteristics, and do not feel pressured. The service sector, which developed after the industrial sector, has sprouted a new society. Post-modern society is a concept that refers to the deconstruction of the relationship between different social elements (Crane, 2003, s. 12-13). That is why following the traces of this transformation when considering concepts such as purchasing behavior, consumer desires, business goals will allow more accurate information to emerge from a research point of view.

The qualities of the current state of consumers can be revealed by examining the changes that the economy has undergone. More than one factor has brought about this change. Many changes in the social, economic, cultural spheres have determined the current consumption habits. The generational classification, which examines consumer habits in US society over generations depending on social transformations, reveals striking information that different generations have different consumer trends. Although this classification has been made only according to American generations, the superiority of this country in the economy and similar consumption habits brought about by globalization are convincing about the validity of the classification.

The classified generations, which are divided into X, Y and Z generations, are divided according to their age groups. The individual member of each group exhibits some distinctive consumer behaviors by internalizing the social culture of the years in which they were born and spent their childhood and youth. Danziger, who writes articles on consumer research, writes that there are four main groups that are active as consumers, and distinguishes them according to age and social events. These are the War Generation, also called the Silent Generation, the Baby Boomers, the X-Generation (Baby

Busters) and the Y-Generation (Echo Boom). This grouping includes a huge mass of consumers, who in total are from 20 to 84 years old. Of these groups, the Baby Boom Generation and its children, the X Generation, stand out as the largest groups that focus on luxury consumption (Danziger, 2006, s. 14-15).

Some luxury brands are aimed at economically strong female consumers in the age range of 30 to 50 years. In contrast, considering that the consumer group that tends to luxury products and services in some Asian countries is around the age of 25, it turns out that the age classification is not the strongest variable (Thomas, 2007, s. 4). Sunday's target market is determined, it is quite difficult to determine the age range. Because there may be subgroups showing similar consumer habits in different age groups. That is why it is so important to choose the right age when determining a group. In addition, in countries where social well-being and purchasing power are high, consumers may turn to luxury consumption even in their later years as their long life expectancy also increases. However, in some sectors, as age progresses, there are trends towards products from different product groups of the same brand. For example, a female consumer who uses the care products of a cosmetics brand in her youth may turn to rejuvenating products of the same brand in her later years (Jackson & Shaw, 2009, s. 18).

Young consumers have a fairly flexible structure in such matters as change, trend and fashion. The spread of a new fashionable outfit can be very fast. But the new fashion is not only for teenagers. It is noteworthy that consumers aged 50 and older are curious about fashion and consumer trends. The assumption that this consumer group will now turn to only certain products and services after a certain age has changed in the opposite direction in recent years. Peter Pan Marketing, named after Peter Pan, a child hero who never grew up, refers to marketing work for a consumer group that has always wanted to achieve luxury products in some sectors, such as clothing, despite its advancing age. Clothing brands that want to reach this audience should ensure that an original fashion culture is established for these consumers. Because the consumers included in this group now have a certain level of income or accumulation. Turning to this area and implementing a flexible pricing policy means a high profit margin for businesses. However, the desire of the middle age group to look younger and various behavioral changes are harbingers of new consumer habits (Jackson and Shaw, 2009, s. 52-53).

Businesses can follow different strategies to reach different target Sundays. Accordingly, a business in the clothing sector cannot always predict which target Sunday will be more profitable. The younger generation stands out because of their frequent shopping habits. But they do not spend a very high amount of money. In turn, the middle-aged and older group can afford high-quality

products with certain income levels. Also noteworthy is the interest of this group in fashion. Sunday's business can create different sub-brands or product groups that will be directed to different target markets and make an original marketing study for each market group. The pricing of different products manufactured for different Sunday groups should coincide with the qualifications of the group. These methods can appeal to a wide range of consumer groups, including baby, child, teenager, student, employee, parent, adult, elderly.

Businesses worldwide are businesses that sell to world Sundays. There are big differences between their target Sundays. Conducting Sunday segmentation and positioning studies in the national or local plane will give a flexible quality to the marketing strategy. Although similar consumer characteristics arise due to global consumption habits, the unique qualities of each region make localization studies necessary in marketing. That is why global enterprises that create subgroups for very different audiences and cater to a large audience will not have a hard time addressing local Sundays. Because it has gained a certain flexibility thanks to the sub-brands it has created.

The consumer group, which is interested in fashion in Turkey and often prefers new products in the clothing sector and spends its expenses in this direction, is usually composed of consumers at a young age. Turkey's participation in global Sundays started after the 1980s. That is why the influence of these economic factors on the formation of the generation born in these years and on consumer habits is undeniable.

The concept of class, which previously appeared in society due to economic power, is a useful concept for individuals to demonstrate the consumption behavior of the class to which they belong. However, the phenomenon of "having a lifestyle", which is different for everyone in post-modern society, establishes a direct link between the expectations of individuals from life and their actions in life and their consumption habits. This concept arose due to the fact that in developed countries there is an opportunity to spend money in multiple areas. The rise of income, which meets only vital needs during the years of the world wars, along with globalization, led to individuals acquiring hobbies and turning to luxury consumption. Luxury consumption, which previously applied to an elite class, has become widespread towards other classes over time (Wallop, 2013, s. 6).

The proliferation of consumer products, the fact that many people belonging to different classes have different desires and preferences, has put pressure on businesses to determine a marketing strategy. Now individuals determine their position in society by the products and services they consume. That is why individuals have focused not only their needs, but also their desires, desires and demands. This group of consumers with a certain level of income is often called the middle class. It is noteworthy that after the mid-1950s, the proportion of

individuals in the UK who considered themselves to be in the middle class increased from 15% to 70%. The increased level of income has revealed the need for an individual to position himself at a different point. But it can not be said that these individuals have a common lifestyle. The judgment that the middle class owns a house and a car is usually one of the common characteristics of this class. Apart from this, it is difficult to determine common characteristics. In addition, the problems experienced by the global economy and the increasing demand for consumption in response to imbalances in income levels have revealed an ambiguous system of consumption habits. Consumer behavior, such as ultra-wealthy individuals shopping for global brands, individuals with very limited income levels owning the most luxurious smartphone in installments, shows that consumption habits belonging to certain consumer groups are becoming unclear (Wallop, 2013, s. 8).

Although the family, education and professional status, which are one of the indicators determining the social position, are still valid, their influence has decreased. However, consumption habits reveal a level in terms of social position. The middle class no longer has a homogeneous structure. Variables such as sub-brands, product diversity, hobbies have ensured the existence of very different social positions. Decisions about consumption show where individuals are located in which class (Wallop, 2013, s. 11). Silverstein and Fiske, who conducted US middle-class studies (2003, s. 48) they have established that individuals belonging to this class now demand higher quality and luxury. The middle class, consisting of individuals who can travel the world with an increased level of income, the desire to be conscious created by information technologies, has the potential to spend more at rates in the range of 20% to 200% for a higher level of quality.

Individuals tend to spend more on products and services that make them seem more exclusive and valuable. Because they perceive the relevant product or service as important. Brands are very variable in choosing a product that they find important to them or not. For example, a consumer who has endured high prices for a luxury car may prefer cheap places for food expenses. The feeling of satisfaction that a luxury car gives to an individual who does not care about his nutrition is above everything (Silverstein & Fiske, 2003, s. 50). In addition, the consumer group, which has a high income level but enjoys following certain promotions and discounts, has also been introduced into the literature with the concept of "Prada and Primark (Jackson & Shaw, 2009, s. 13).

Bill Webb draws attention to the following features regarding the preferences of the new consumer (Webb, 2001, s. 70-72):

- The new consumer rejects the traditional class system and uses the typical characteristics of his class it is the

consumer who has a compulsive consumption habit. The wishes and wishes of this group demands they form in the direction of. That is why it is quite difficult to clearly determine this group. The desire of each person to be unique leads to the emergence of a large number of desires and desires has been. It is impossible to clearly solve this complex structure. Individuals the factors that make up their personality are income level, lifestyle, reference group, current it is a cultural and social environment. Despite this, the new consumer feels free it is wrapped. Individuality is at the forefront. These are products and services for individuals. They are the most important elements that determine its quality. For these individuals who feel very special the concept of a family is a decoupling of special individuals from each other, each according to his own taste it has products and uses common living spaces in a democratic way it is a concept related to the transformation of environments into a way of life.

- New consumers have differentiated products and services because they feel special tend to. That is why businesses offer products and services that show a feeling of satisfaction he tries to design it. That is why businesses are constantly doing Sunday research to target they destroy the desires and aspirations of the Sunday. If a change has occurred in the target Sunday, the new keeping up with the situation immediately can be of critical importance for the enterprise. The opportunity to save a lot of money on the subject.

- New consumers are more stable. How to get which product from which enterprise when they have already
- The needs of new consumers are diversifying over time. With physical needs together, consumers who meet their security needs to a large extent spend their free time he tries to satisfy the needs of self-realization in most of them. Consumers ' hobbies this is necessary by acquiring, designing various activities and creating social groups he tries to meet it. In order to meet the requests and demands related to these areas, the enterprises new consumers in the target Sunday need to discover these aspects.

- New consumers internalize individuality and move away from the understanding of unity it is understood from the decrease in the number of social groups. However, the social aspect of individuals he always hears about the need to get together with other people, because they are high dec. This it is inevitable that social groups created from the face will be brought together with brand thinking he's probably here. A variety of social groups formed by fans who support a sports team an example of this is when brands come together and carry out activities sponsored by Dec. One an example of this is the hobby groups, where users of the motorcycle brand gather Dec it can be shown as.

- A high level of education, increased income, a great knowledge thanks to the possibilities of the Internet convincing a new consumer who has an accumulation of

traditional marketing methods it is difficult. In addition, consumers have all the staff they employ, which does not harm nature consciously identify businesses that provide their rights and avoid excessive pricing and they follow. That is why enterprises use every aspect of their production and marketing strategies he must gracefully establish his step. Day by day, the possibilities of reaching global brands with the increase of consumers who think that foreign enterprises offer better services, this it will be very easy for him to immediately turn to brands.

- The new consumer values time more than money. The intensity of working hours, in traffic the last hours, the hours spent at home preparing for work, the time devoted to personal care, the new it offers consumers a fairly limited amount of free time. This is the most productive free time individuals who want to use it in this way are open to innovations and quick solutions. That's why some processes are focused on the distribution and delivery of the product rather than the product. Modular furniture, purchased and installed immediately, immediately harmonized with fashion clothes can be cited as an example of this situation. To be at the forefront of the race against time the desiring enterprise is aware that it will become the most valuable in the eyes of the consumer. Ready restaurants offering food, valets parking the car, who immediately respond to the health problem special consultation lines, self-payment systems that solve the november of the cash queue, such as the basis of the services is to save time for the new consumer. His free time the new consumer, who wants to increase it, will also turn to the enterprises providing these services. E-trading also allows the new consumer to move the entire shopping process to an electronic environment it offers determined what they will do. Very powerful advertising messages, new type it may be ineffective in the consumer. Offering authoritative ideas about the brand and business channels are of no great importance to new consumers. Because the new consumer he's already made his decision.

- The variety and range of products is not always important for the new consumer. The important thing is it is the value that the product will add to the life of the consumer. That's why the new consumer, shopping he approaches his phenomenon in a multidimensional way.

Universal Consumer Rights

It is seen that the effectiveness and speed of dissemination of consumer rights and consumer protection activities has increased even more since the 1980s, especially with the introduction of the Internet into our lives (Altunışık, Mert, & Nart, 2004, s. 477). The most notable of the universally accepted legal regulations for the protection of consumers is the "United Nations Declaration on Universal Consumer Rights" of 1985. The

eight basic consumer rights published in this declaration have also become valid for the Turkish consumer with the Law on Consumer Protection No. 4077, which entered into force on September 8, 1995 in our country. The eight basic consumer rights declared in this declaration have been interpreted by different sections in the literature and evaluated in terms of marketing direction.

The Right to Eliminate Basic Requirements: This right refers to the minimum needs necessary for individuals to continue their lives and ensures that basic necessities products reach consumers at an affordable price and with good quality. The products mentioned here include basic food, clothing, housing and health services (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014, s. 67).

The Right to Security: It is the most important of the fundamental rights, since it directly concerns the life and health of the consumer. The element of standardization has become an indispensable part of the issue of consumer rights under the right to security. Thus, it is ensured that consumers are protected against the marketing of products that are harmful to their lives and health. In order not to violate this right, manufacturers are required to conduct a comprehensive safety and performance test before bringing their products to Sunday (Ibarra and Revilla, 2014, s. 68).

Right To Information: Consumers have the right to receive the necessary information about the relevant products in the purchase process. At the same time, consumers should not be exposed to deceptive advertising, packaging and labeling in order to make the right decision. Information provided to consumers, product specifications, price, method of payment, safety warnings, usage, content, warranty period, description of after-sales services, expiration date, etc. information includes (Ibarra and Revilla, 2014, s. 68).

choice: With this right, consumers can access various products and services at any time (Altunışık, Mert, & Nart, 2004, s. 477). It is aimed to improve the quality element and become satisfactory by offering goods and services to the consumer at competitive prices along with diversity. The right to choose also seeks to protect competitors from each other, especially small firms, from large and powerful ones (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014, s. 68).

The Right to Organize and be Represented (to Make Your Voice Heard): The right to make his voice heard includes an assurance that the consumer will be considered and represented in the formulation of government policies and during regulatory procedures. It can be considered the most effective method for consumers to unite and form a power union in order to protect their rights and decouple their grievances (Babaoğul and Altrok, 2007, s. 38).

The Right to Compensation: The right to compensation specifies the elimination of losses in cases where the consumer is a victim (Altunışık, Mert, & Nart, 2004, s. 477). Accordingly, consumers may request that defective or defective products be replaced or refunded

(Ibarra and Revilla, 2014, s. 68). It will be possible to ensure that the justified demands of consumers are taken into account and met by enterprises and other organizations with this right.

The Right To Be Trained: Education, which is the main element of ensuring development in almost every field, is also an indispensable element in addressing a comprehensive issue in which the consumer is the focus. In order to prevent the exploitation of consumers, consumer awareness and education are essentially necessary. Various seminars, conferences, etc. open to the public for consumer welfare by business and government agencies on this issue. information campaigns are carried out in the form of (Ibarra & Revilla, 2014, s. 68).

The Right to Have a Healthy Environment: It is also a basic consumer right to expect enterprises to produce without harming the environment. With this right, the necessity of protecting the environment with the correct use of natural resources has been expressed in order for current and future generations to live in a healthy environment (Altunışık, Mert, & Nart, 2004, s. 477).

RESULT

Decisions to use the values at their disposal (money, time, credit, power) in order to best meet the needs of consumers are called consumer behavior. In other words, it is the entire decision process of consumers regarding which product or service to buy, how, where, from whom, when and whether to buy it. In today's world, where sunday conditions are constantly changing, the behavior of consumers when buying products and services is changing at the same rate. Nowadays, it has become quite difficult to please consumers. In order to respond to the changing needs and desires of consumers, it is necessary to get to know the consumer very well. Good recognition of the consumer means that elements such as what he first cares about when making a purchase behavior, what encourages him to buy, etc. are known (Tokol, 1983, s. 76).

In this study, consumer behavior was considered in the general context and universal consumer rights were evaluated. As a result of the study, it is understood that the concept of consumer and consumer behavior is in the process of a major change in the competitive environment, which is increasing with the developing technology and globalization. In this context, consumer rights are expected to develop and change within the framework of this change.

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